

DIFFUSION BONDING OF DISCONTINUOUS SILICON CARBIDE/ALUMINIUM ALLOY
(SiC_p/Al) METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE.

A. Ureña, J.M. Gómez de Salazar
Dpto. Ciencia de los Materiales e Ingeniería Metalúrgica.
Facultad de Ciencias Químicas
Universidad Complutense de Madrid.
SPAIN

A B S T R A C T

Solid state bonded joints in a metal-matrix composite containing 12 vol% silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) dispersed in a matrix of aluminium-copper alloy (AA 2124) have been produced using different laminar metallic interlayers. The effects of bonding parameters (temperature and pressure), postbonding heat treatments and insert metallic films on the microstructural characteristics of the bond interfaces have been systematically investigated. The metallic interlayers used were : (i) aluminium-lithium alloy (AA 8090), (ii) superplastic aluminium-copper alloy (Supral 100) and (iii) pure silver. Diffusion profiles of alloying elements from the metal matrix to the interlayers and "vice versa", have been determined by EDS microanalysis. These studies have been completed with microhardness measures, specially to determinate the lithium diffusion when AA 8090 interlayer was applied.

KEY WORDS: diffusion bonding, composite, aluminium alloy, silicon-carbide, superplastic alloy, silver interlayer.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the problems which avoid the extensive application of metal matrix composites in structures is their joining. For this reason, it is necessary to develop techniques for obtaining strength unions between MMCs and heterogeneous unions with other structural metallic alloys (aluminium, titanium, steels, etc). Solid state diffusion bonding is an attractive method for joining MMC since it avoids the microstructural degradation associated with conventional fusion welding processes (change in the array of fibers and deterioration of them)(1). Beside diffusion bonding has a higher design flexibility than other joining techniques studied by several investigators, such as resistant spot welding (2), brazing (3) or friction welding (4).

However, diffusion bonding of aluminium alloys is difficult because the protective oxide film (Al₂O₃) present on the metal surface, which

prevents the formation of the necessary metallic contact to obtain a solid state union (5). It makes necessary to use different interlayer coatings or foils (Cu, Ag or Zn) to facilitate the bond formation (6-8). However, the inclusion of these intermediate metals produces a change of the composition in the bond region, with formation of intermetallic compounds which decrease the bond strength.

Diffusion bonding of aluminium MMCs also shows the previous difficulty. Besides, the use of interlayers (metallic foils) produces a change in the number and distribution of the reinforce particles in the bond regions, which conditions the mechanical properties of the joint (9).

In the present investigation, in order to select the optimum metallic interlayer to bond an Al-Cu 2124 alloy reinforced with silicon carbide particles (SiC_p); three different interlayers have been used:

- i) Al-2.4Li alloy (AA 8090)
- ii) Al-5.9Cu superplastic alloy (Supral 100)
- iii) pure silver

Two first interlayer were selected because their similar compositions to the metallic matrix of the composite, but with the presence of some alloying elements (Li, Cu) which could facilitate the solid state bonding. Silver was used because the Al-Ag intermetallic compounds are less brittle than others.

Present paper shows the results of these investigations, specially those related with the microstructural changes occurred in the bond interfaces and the effects of the bonding parameters and postbonding heat treatments on them.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials.

The parent material used was a discontinuous reinforced metal matrix composite containing 12 vol% silicon carbide particles in Al-Cu alloy (AA 2124) with a chemical composition as is shown in Table 1. It was received in the form of a 6 mm thick sheet, with the standard T6 treatment of the AA 2124. The particles showed a preferential alignment in the direction of lamination.

Three different interlayers were used: and aluminium-lithium foil of 150 μm thick obtained from cold rolled of a 1.5 mm thick sheet with a T6 condition; an aluminium-copper superplastic alloy (SUPRAL 100) applied in form of 150 μm foil, obtained by grinding of a 1 mm sheet; and a 15-30 μm thick foil of pure silver. In some bonded trials aluminium alloys interlayer were ground to thickness close to 50 μm . Chemical composition of these interlayers are also shown in Table 1.

2.2 Diffusion bonding.

Specimens of 6*12.5 mm² were cut from the base composite sheet and the surfaces to be bonded were ground using progressively finer emery paper down to 1200 grade. They were then cleaned and degreased

in an ultrasonic bath with acetone. Afterwards, specimens were chemically cleaned with a commercial desoxidant for aluminium alloys (Turco 4). Interlayer foils were prepared in the same way than MMC, with exception of silver foils which were not chemically treated.

Diffusion bonding trials were carried out using a modified vacuum furnace with a pressure application system. It has been described in previous paper (10). The effect of temperature in the range of 470-520 °C and of applied pressure (between 3 and 6 MPa) were studied. The bonding time used was always 60 min. and every bonding trials were carried out in a vacuum atmosphere of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ Torr (10^{-2} Pa). Final thickness deformation introduced in the specimens after bonding cycles was controlled.

After bonding some specimens were heat treated. Solution heat treatment (SHT) at 500 °C during 4-8 hour followed by cold water quenching (Q), and occasionally artificial ageing at 191 °C during 16 hours, were applied.

2.3. Microstructural studies.

Metallographic sections through the bond regions (axial) were prepared by grinding and polishing with conventional techniques. Microstructures were studied after etching with Keller's reagent. Optical microscopy was usually followed by examination with scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Composition in the bond regions were determined by energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS). Microhardness measurement across the bond interfaces were also applied as an indirect method to determine the diffusion of lithium when AA 8090 interlayer was used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Diffusion bonding using AA 8090 interlayer.

Figure 1 shows the as-bonded microstructure of a MMC-MMC joint using an aluminium-lithium alloy (AA 8090), in form of a 150 μm thick foil, as interlayer. The bonding condition for this trial were: temperature of 500 °C, pressure of 6 MPa and 60 minutes of bonding time. Several phenomena originated by bonding cycle can be observed: (1) AA 8090 interlayer suffers a heterogeneous deformation reducing its thickness under 80 μm ; (2) there is a massive precipitation of particles in the foil interlayer, specially of rich copper phases (CuAl_2 - θ phase); (3) there is no sign of the original interface.

The high plasticity of the AA 8090 alloy at the bonding conditions originated the plastic flow of the foil which even disappeared in some zones (Figure 2). The SiC particle distribution in these zones is very uniform and similar to the bulk MMC. However, the high bulk deformation produced during the bonding cycle (45%) generates some banding and clustering of the particles in the MMC.

The presence of high proportion of θ phase in the AA 8090 interlayer only can be explained by diffusion of copper from the 2124 matrix of composite to the aluminium-lithium interlayer. The postbonding heat

treatment applied (SHT+Q) provided the almost complete solubilization of the interlayer precipitates and reveal the recrystallization and grain growth of the 8090 across the bond interface, being observed SiC reinforced particles inside the new grains (Figure 3).

Decreasing the bonding pressure down to 3 MPa is possible to limitate the MMC bulk deformation under 25% without loss of high integrity microstructure in the bond interface. However, under these conditions, the interlayer was homogeneously deformed down to 120 μm thick (Figure 3). Microhardness measurements in this specimen after postbonding heat treatment (SHT+Q+ageing), show a softening of the interlayer regions close to the bond interface and an increase of the MMC hardness in the vicinity of both bond lines (Figure 4). Both phenomena can be only explained by the lithium diffusion from the interlayer to the MMC. The enrichment of MMC in lithium favours the strengthening of 2124 matrix (11) and improves the SiC/matrix bond as has shown Webster (12).

Decreasing bonding temperature (480 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and increasing bonding pressure (6 MPa) is possible to obtain microstructures similar than Figure 3, but with lower thickness reduction in the specimens (<10%). However, if the bonding temperature is lower than 480 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, interfaces with high proportion of residual porosity are obtained. In these bonds, interfaces with a marked planarity and SiC particles aligned in them are usually distinguished (Figure 5).

This study allows to deduce that lithium plays an important role in the obtention of a high quality joint in an aluminium matrix composite. It is because the high activity of lithium, which favours its reaction with the aluminium protective film, producing its partial disruption by formation of less hard and insoluble oxides (LiO_2 , LiAlO_2 , LiAl_5O_8) (13). (Table II)

3.2 Diffusion bonding using SUPRAL 100 interlayer.

Solid state bonding of MMC with SUPRAL interlayer at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 6 MPa and 60 minutes, origins again a high thickness reduction in the bonded specimen ($\cong 45\%$). However, in contrast with joints bonded using Al-Li interlayer at the same conditions, the deformation produced in the SUPRAL foil is homogeneous, reducing its thickness from 150 μm to 60 μm (Figure 6). Microstructural studies of the as-bonded specimen show the achievement of a high quality joint with a bond interface free of residual porosity, and the precipitation of rich-copper particles in the interlayer and in the composite matrix. Recrystallization and grain growth of the interlayer across the bond interface are observed in solubilized joints. However, studies at higher magnification show the presence of a very fine unsolubilized precipitates localized at the bond interface, which probably conditions the bond strength (Figure 7).

Bonding with lower pressure (3 MPa) was possible to generate a lower deformation in the MMC pieces (<30%). However, although the interfaces keep a high continuity degree without porosity, the proportion of unsolubilized precipitates in the bond interface is

higher (Figure 8).

Copper concentration profiles obtained by punctual quantitative microanalysis across the bond interface show the copper enrichment in the matrix composite close to the bond interface. However, copper diffusion is very limited, in spite of the long bonding time applied followed by the solution heat treatment (2 h in this case) (Figure 9).

3.3. Diffusion bonding using silver interlayer.

Joints bonded with silver foils showed microstructural characteristics completely different to the previous ones. Solid state bonding with Ag favours the formation of an Al-Ag intermetallic compound layer which has been identified by EDS as δ phase (14.3% Al-85.7% Ag) (Figure 10).

In specimens bonded at 480 °C, 3 MPa and 60 min using a 50 μm thick silver foil, the intermetallic layer grows towards the MMC forming a 7-8 μm thick band of δ phase with SiC particles inserted in it (Figure 11). The presence of δ phase were also observed in the composite matrix in form of fine needles with a typical Widmanstätten morphology. Besides, aluminium needles with silver in solid solution were detected in the intermetallic compound layer (Figure 12).

The formation of a SiC- δ phase band has not observed in specimens bonded at 500 °C, 3 MPa and 60 min, with only 20 μm of silver interlayer, although reaction zones between SiC and silver has been detected using backscattered images (Figure 13).

The application of a SHT (500 °C - 7,5 h) followed by quenching, to solubilize the intermetallic layer, promotes a degradation of the joint because the oxidation of the intermetallic compounds, specially, in the MMC- δ phase interface. However, there were zones of partial solubilization without oxide formation (Figure 14).

4. CONCLUSIONS.

- 1). High bond quality can be obtained in MMC diffusion joints using Al-Li interlayer with strengthening of the bond interface because the Li enrichment of MMC. However, to produce it, is necessary to bond using high macroscopic deformation (>20%).
- 2). Diffusion bonding of MMC using SUPRAL interlayers present problems of interfacial precipitates formation, specially when bonding pressure decreased.
- 3). Silver interlayer origins the formation of brittle intermetallic compounds, which suffers a rapid oxidation when joints are solubilized heat treated in air furnaces. Reaction zones between silver and SiC particles has been detected.

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Table I.- Chemical composition of parent materials.

ALLOY	Cu	Li	Mg	Mn	Si	Fe	Zr	Cr	Ti	Zn	Sn	Na
AA2124	4.4	-	1.5	0.5	0.2	0.3	-	0.10	0.10	0.25	-	-
AA8090	1.2	2.4	0.6	-	0.03	0.07	0.14	-	-	-	-	<0.001
SUPRAL 100	5.9	-	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.16	-	<0.01	<0.01	<0.02	<0.01	-

Table II.- Chemical reaction between Li and Al Oxide Layer. Gibss Free Energy at 530 °C.

Reaction	ΔG° (kJ/mol)
$\text{Li} + 1/3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{LiO}_2 + 2/3\text{Al}$	- 19
$\text{Li} + 8/3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{LiAl}_3\text{O}_8 + 1/3\text{Al}$	- 36
$\text{Li} + 2/3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{LiAlO}_2 + 1/3\text{Al}$	- 68

Fig.-1 MMC-MMC joint with AA8090 interlayer (500°C, 6MPa, 60min)

Fig.-2 Detail of bond zone with complete elimination interlayer

Fig.-3 Recrystallization and grain growth across bond interface.

Fig.-4 Microhardness profile in a MMC-8090-MMC diffusion joint.

Fig.-5 MMC-AA8090 joint bonded at 470°C with interfacial porosity

Fig.-6 MMC-MMC joint with SUPRAL 100 interlayer (500°C, 6MPa, 60min)

Fig.-7 MMC-SUPRAL interface with unsolubilized precipitates.

Fig.-8 MMC-SUPRAL interface bonded with a bonding pressure of 3MPa

Fig.-9 Copper concentration profile in a MMC-SUPRAL-MMC joint

Fig.-10 MMC-MMC joint with pure silver interlayer.

Fig.-11 MCC- δ phase interface with formation of SiC/ δ phase band.

Fig.-12 Precipitation of δ needles in 2124 matrix of composite (Al) in δ compound layer

Fig.-13 BSE imagen of SiC particles in δ phase. Reactions zones

Fig.-14 Interfacial oxidation in a SHT MMC-Ag joint. (A): δ phase. (B): oxide. (C): Al